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Forecasting Vegetable Production in the Tashkent Region: Economic Analysis and Development Prospects

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the forecasting of vegetable production volumes in the Tashkent region using statistical and economic approaches. Time series methods, correlation analysis, and multifactor regression models were applied to data from 2010–2024 to identify the key factors influencing production levels and to develop forecast indicators for 2025–2030. The results indicate that vegetable production in the region is likely to maintain stable growth trends, supported by increased investment, the introduction of modern technologies, and improvements in productivity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Vegetable growing is one of the important directions of the agricultural sector, which is of great importance in ensuring food security of the population, forming a raw material base for the processing industry, and offering competitive products in the domestic and foreign markets. Tashkent region is one of the main vegetable-growing regions in Uzbekistan in terms of climatic conditions, irrigated land and labor resources. Therefore, accurate and reliable forecasting of production volumes is an important task in regional agricultural policy, planning investment projects and assessing market conditions. The purpose of this study is to identify the main drivers of vegetable production in the Tashkent region and to develop a forecast model for 2025–2030.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Scientific research on forecasting the volume of vegetable production has been widely studied both in world practice and in Uzbekistan. The literature primarily emphasizes the importance of climate factors, efficient use of land resources, intensive technologies, and investment activity in the development of agricultural sectors.

In international sources (FAO), climate conditions, yield dynamics, the effectiveness of irrigation technologies, and changes in market

demand are noted as the main factors in forecasting the volume of vegetable production. The research conducted by Uzbek scientists highlights the theoretical and practical foundations for modernizing agriculture, developing intensive horticulture, and increasing the agricultural potential of the regions. In particular, B.T. Salimov, M.S. Yusupov, A.S. Yusupov in their research work assessed the organizational structure and features of development, conjuncture, commodity and geographical composition of world agricultural and food markets, indicators of competition and competitiveness of food products in them, the conditions for the production, storage, processing and export of fruit and vegetable products to world markets in the agro-industrial complex of Uzbekistan, as well as the integration of the industry into world trade systems.

Some researchers have presented empirical evidence of a multiple increase in yields in areas where intensive horticulture and modern irrigation systems have been implemented. At the same time, it has been shown that multifactorial regression models built on the basis of regional variables have high accuracy in forecasting the volume of fruit and vegetable production.

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3. RESEARCH METHODS

In the research process, comparison, monographic study, statistical and econometric modeling, economic analysis and synthesis, the ARIMA (ARMA) model, and other methods were used.

Research results. Within the framework of the study, the following factors influencing the effectiveness of attracting investments in the fruit and vegetable sector were identified for the model, namely:

- Volume of vegetable production, tons;
- Total sown area, ha;
- Average annual temperature, °C;
- Volume of investments in the fruit and vegetable industry, in million soums;
- Population employed in agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, thousand people.

Based on the above factors, based on the analysis of the state of fruit and vegetable production in the Tashkent region in 2010-2024, where monographic research was conducted, calculations were carried out to determine the prospects for the volume of fruit and vegetable production in the region in 2025-2029 (Table 1).

Table 1.

Dynamics of vegetable production in the Tashkent region in 2010-2024

Years	*Value of vegetable production, tons	*Total sown area, ha	** Average annual temperature, °C	*Volume of investments in the fruit and vegetable industry, in million soums	*Number of people employed in agriculture, forestry and fisheries, thousand people
2010	1,215,042	31,758	14	51,684.0	312,2
2011	1,253,028	31,466	14	69,397.0	324,8
2012	1,286,683	33,726	15	93,947.0	311,5
2013	1,323,491	34,197	15	125,182.0	323,1
2014	1,352,862	33,672	15	165,728.0	325,3
2015	1,368,247	33,289	15	205,491.0	331
2016	1,372,062	36,805	15	210,194.0	335,1
2017	1,238,653	25,698	15	401,564.0	338,4
2018	1,081,247	25,484	16	649,718.0	322,9
2019	1,065,771	23,537	16	873,943.0	322,2
2020	1,038,913	24,803	16	1,068,222.0	304,2
2021	1,039,584	23,899	16	733,004.0	279,5
2022	1,101,489	24,489	16	505,225.0	283,1
2023	1,154,655	26,616	16	413,715.0	288,3
2024	1,194,831	28,535	17	398,429.0	273,6

Note: * - Data from the Department of Agriculture of Tashkent region.

** - Data from the Tashkent Regional Meteorological Station (M-II) of the Center for Hydrometeorological Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In particular, the analysis of the average, maximum, and minimum indicators of independent and dependent variables, such as the volume of fruit and vegetable production in the Tashkent region in 2010-2024, the total sown area, the average annual temperature, the volume of

investments in the fruit and vegetable industry, the number of people employed in agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, was carried out using the Stata 16 program.

According to the analysis, for example, during the selected years (2010-2024), the total volume of vegetable production was a maximum of 1,372,062 tons, and a minimum of 1,038,913 tons.

Figure 1. Correlation matrix of the relationship of factors using the Stata 16 program.

* Compiled by the author using the Stata16 program

According to the correlation analysis of the interrelationships of the factors isolated for the model, the resulting factor is a very strong and direct correlation (0.9239) between the volume of vegetable production and the area of vegetable crops. This is explained by the fact that the volume of vegetable production naturally depends on the area of production. There is also an inverse and moderately strong correlation (-0.6262) between the average annual temperature and the volume of vegetables. This means that in some cases, an increase in temperature can have a negative impact on productivity, for example, due to extremely hot days or drought, which can reduce yields. In addition, an inverse and quite strong correlation (-0.7389) is also observed between the volume of investments in the fruit and vegetable sector and the volume of vegetables. This can be explained by the fact that investments are mainly directed to infrastructure, equipment or projects that will bear fruit in the future and are not immediately reflected in the volume of crops. At the same time, there is a weak positive correlation (0.5506) between the number of employed people in agriculture, forestry and fisheries and the volume of vegetables. This increase in employment may be associated with an increase in labor resources in agricultural production (Figure 1).

The correlation results show that some factors in the model have a strong influence on the outcome indicator, while others have only a partial influence. In this regard, it is appropriate to separately check which factors are statistically significant in the regression model at the next stage.

When examining the results of the regression analysis between factors, it can be seen that due to the different nature of the variables used in the model, it is difficult to substantiate some coefficients. This is because the indicators included in the model, such as vegetable cultivation area, average annual temperature, investment volume, and population employment, belong to different areas in terms of economic content, and their mechanisms of influence differ from each other. Therefore, it is not always possible to determine the direct effect between factors and fully substantiate the regression results.

At the same time, since the units of measurement of the factors differ significantly from each other, all indicators were converted to logarithmic form in order to bring them to the same scale. This process serves to increase the accuracy of the model and facilitate the analytical interpretation of the coefficients.

A regression analysis was carried out using the logarithmic values of such indicators as the volume of vegetable production, the area of vegetable cultivation, annual average temperature, agricultural investments, and employment of the population, and a model was formed. Although the model has a high explanatory power in general, the meaningful interpretation of some coefficients requires caution due to the different nature of the factors and possible multicollinearity (Figure 2).

factors, and external economic conditions, the volume decreased sharply, reaching 1,038,913 tons by 2020. Starting in 2021, the sector began to recover, and in 2024, the volume exceeded 1,194,831 tons.

4. CONCLUSION.

According to the results of the forecast model, the volume of vegetable production in the Tashkent region is expected to grow at a partially stable and slow pace during the period 2025-2030. In particular, in 2025, the volume is forecast to reach 1,193,937 tons, and in subsequent years it is forecast to gradually increase, reaching 1,196,556 tons in 2028, 1,196,990 tons in 2029, and 1,197,303 tons by 2030.

This moderate growth, which is observed in the forecast, is primarily due to the preservation of the total area of crops without significant changes, the absence of significant negative changes in climatic conditions, the consistent growth of investments in the fruit and vegetable sector, and the increase in the potential of the employed population in agriculture. At the same time, factors such as the use of modern agrotechnologies based on scientific and practical approaches, the modernization of irrigation systems, and the efficient use of resources can also enhance the growth potential of the sector. From this point of view, in order to ensure the sustainable growth of the vegetable sector in the Tashkent region in the coming years, one of the important tasks is to introduce development strategies in accordance with the natural and climatic conditions of the region, support investment activity, and increase the efficiency of labor resources.

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